

Reactions of Nickel(II) with Acid and Base Saturated Montmorillonites

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The effects of time, pH and temperature on the interaction of nickel with H-, Na- and Ca- saturated montmorillonites have been investigated. Maximum adsorption occurs at pH 6 while before and after it (pH 6) adsorption declines. The adsorption increased rapidly and then slowly with increase in the time of interaction. The values of rate constants and the half times of reaction suggested an exchange process controlled by film and particle diffusion. The inferences were confirmed from the nature of adsorption isotherms. Temperature affected the adsorption with exothermic nature of interactions. The activation energy of adsorption of nickel on Na- and Ca-, montmorillonite was 10.2 and 10.6 k cal mole respectively.

AMONG the heavy metals used as micronutrients nickel salts especially nickel chloride has been recognised as a valuable fertilizer and fungicide¹. A little work on the interaction of Ni(II) with clays and soils has been reported so far. The adsorption of Ni(II) in soils is affected by pH, organic matter and oxidation-reduction status of soils. The study of interaction of Ni(II) ions with clay minerals has been increasing in recent years². Hathway and Lewis³ by electronic absorption spectra of Ni(II) adsorption on silica gel reported that Ni(II) exists on the surface in a chemical form similar to that found in solution, Dugger *et al*⁴ have reported the thermodynamic parameters for adsorption of Ni(II) on silica and Swartzen-Allen and Matijevic⁵ have reviewed the quantitative aspect of Ni(II) adsorption.

Montmorillonite is an important constituent of basaltic vertisol soils which occur so widely all over the world. The mineral possesses a high cation exchange capacity and has been known to provide heterogeneous chemically reactive spots on its surface in the form of exchangeable cations, sorbed water cations, hydroxyl groups and lattice surface oxygens.

The primary objective of this work is to investigate the interaction and mechanism of adsorption of Ni(II), a typical fungicide on suspended montmorillonite particles in their acid and base saturated forms.

Experimental

The bentonite used in these studies was obtained from Akli in Rajasthan. The <2 μ m fraction was purified by sedimentation and centrifugation. X-ray diffraction revealed that main constituent of this bentonite was montmorillonite. The suspension

was then converted into chloride free Na- and H-saturated montmorillonites by Aldrich and Buchanan's method⁶. Ca-saturated montmorillonite was prepared from the sodium form by an ion exchange technique. The concentration of the suspensions ranged from 15.0 to 16.5 g l⁻¹. The cation exchange capacity (CEC) as determined by Ganguli's method⁷ was 72 meq per 100 g clay.

To study the effect of time, 10 ml of the clay suspension in their H-, Na- and Ca-forms were taken in several glass stoppered tubes and treated with 3, 5, 7 and 15 ml of 0.015 M NiCl₂ at 30°. Further one set with 15 ml of nickel chloride and 10 ml of H-, Na- and Ca- montmorillonites was also treated at 60°. The volume of the mixtures was made up to 25 ml with distilled water, the samples were then shaken for various periods ranging between 1/4 to 6 hours, then centrifuged and nickel estimated in the supernatant solution measured by EDTA titration using PAN as indicator. The extent of adsorption was estimated by the difference between the amount of nickel added and remaining in the supernatants. The results are given in Fig. 1.

The effect of the equilibrium pH on experiment was investigated at different pH values ranging from 2 to 10. Different pH values are obtained by adding 0.1 N HCl or 0.1N NaOH as required. 10 ml of appropriate clay suspension and 1, 2, 5 and 15 ml of 0.015M nickel chloride were shaken in several glass stoppered tubes. After making the volume 25 ml with distilled water the tubes were shaken for 3 hours, centrifuged and the nickel adsorbed calculated as above.

Experiments for a study of adsorption isotherms were conducted at pH values of the unamended H-, Na- and Ca- montmorillonite suspensions by taking 10 ml suspension of appropriate clay in a

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large number of glass stoppered tubes, adding various concentrations of 0.015M nickel chloride, adjusting the mixtures to 25 ml with distilled water and shaking the tubes at 30° in the first set of experiments and 60° in the second set for 3 hrs in each case. The suspensions were then centrifuged and the residual nickel estimated with standard EDTA solution using PAN as indicator. The difference gave the amount of nickel adsorbed. A plot of the adsorption isotherms is given in Fig. 3.

The results of desorption of nickel from complexed montmorillonites with 0.1N NaCl, 0.1M KCl and 0.05 M BaCl₂ with a shaking time of 6 hrs are given in Table 2.

All the experiments were done in duplicate with suitable blanks.

Results and Discussion

The amount of nickel adsorbed as a function of time is plotted in Fig. 1 for different concentrations

Fig. 1(a). Effect of time on the adsorption of nickel by H-montmorillonite at 30° and 60°. Concentration of nickel in meq per 100 g clay for curve 1=1.0, for curve 2=100.0, for curve 3=140.0 and for curve 4=300.0 at 30° and for curve 5=300.0 at 60°.

1(b). Effect of time on the adsorption of nickel by Na-montmorillonites at 30° and 60°. Concentration of nickel in meq per 100 g clay for curve 1=54.5, for curve 2=10.9, for curve 3=127.3 and for curve 4=272.7 at 30° and curve 5=272.7 at 60°.

1(c). Effect of time on the adsorption of nickel by Ca-montmorillonite at 30° and 60°. Concentration of nickel in meq per 100 g clay for curve 1=56.2, for curve 2=93.8, for curve 3=131.3 and for curve 4=281.3 at 30° and curve 5=281.3 at 60°.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the adsorption of nickel by H(O)-, Na(●) and Ca(X) montmorillonites.

Fig. 3. Adsorption isotherms of H-, Na- and Ca-montmorillonites at 30° and 60° 1, ● Na-mont. at 30°, 2. Δ H-mont. at 30°, 3. × Ca-mont. at 30°, 4. ○ Na-mont. at 60°; 5. ▲ H-mont. at 60° and 6. ● Ca-mont. at 60°.

of nickel chloride added to the H-, Na- and Ca-montmorillonite respectively. The system approaches equilibrium within 3 hrs, initially adsorption is rapid and then there is a slow increase. The initial rapid adsorption may be due to reversible exchange between nickel ions and the replaceable H-, Na- or Ca- ions of the clay surface. The slower increase in adsorption after 1½ hr was either due to slow penetration of Ni(II) ions to clay or due to chemical forces. Fig. 1 also indicates that the amount of nickel adsorption increases as the amount of nickel

TABLE I—EFFECT OF TIME ON THE REACTION OF NICKEL WITH H-, Na- AND Ca-MONTMORILLONITES AT 30° AND 60°C

Time in minutes	30°C								
	H-montmorillonite			Na-montmorillonite			Ca-montmorillonite		
	Conc. of nickel in meq/100 g clay	$k_1 \text{ min}^{-1} \times 10^3$	$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k_1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	Conc. of nickel in meq/100 g clay	$k_1 \text{ min}^{-1} \times 10^3$	$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k_1} \text{ min}^{-1}$	Conc. of nickel in meq/100 g clay	$k_1 \text{ min}^{-1} \times 10^3$	$t_{1/2} = \frac{0.693}{k_1} \text{ min}^{-1}$
15		2.26	307		2.87	242		2.16	321
30		2.36	293		2.87	242		2.14	324
45	60.0	2.30	301	54.5	2.74	253	56.2	2.17	319
60		2.32	300		2.79	248		2.15	322
90		2.30	301		2.76	251		2.19	317
100		1.49	485		1.72	403		1.21	572
15		3.18	218		3.78	183		2.90	239
30		3.18	218		3.76	184		2.93	237
45	100.0	3.25	213	90.9	3.80	182	93.8	2.90	239
60		3.24	214		3.89	180		2.90	239
90		3.21	216		3.85	181		2.93	237
100		2.04	339		2.30	301		1.58	432
15		3.82	181		4.50	154		3.52	197
30		3.80	182		4.48	155		3.48	199
45	140.0	3.84	180	127.3	4.60	150	131.3	3.48	199
60		3.87	179		4.53	153		3.52	197
90		3.86	179		4.58	151		3.50	198
180		2.53	274		2.92	237		1.97	352
15		4.22	164		4.96	140		3.99	174
30		4.24	163		4.93	141		4.00	173
45	300.0	4.28	162	272.7	4.98	140	281.3	4.04	172
60		4.28	162		4.90	142		4.04	172
90		3.16	216		3.51	198		3.23	214
180		1.66	417		1.89	361		1.69	410
Average value		3.64	214		4.19	187		3.60	219
	60°C								
15		4.15	155		5.19	134		4.22	164
30		4.39	158		5.14	135		4.19	165
45	300.0	4.41	157	272.7	5.10	136	281.3	4.18	165
60		4.43	156		5.09	136		4.15	167
90		3.10	224		3.49	198		3.29	210
180		1.60	433		1.83	379		1.67	415
Average value		3.73	213		4.31	186		3.62	215

ions added to the aqueous suspension of clays increases, while with increase in temperature there is a decrease in the adsorption of nickel ions.

Applying the simple kinetic rate laws the order of reaction with respect to nickel was studied at different concentrations of nickel chloride and at fixed concentration of the H-, Na- and Ca- montmorillonites. The reaction followed the first order kinetics

$$K = \frac{2.303}{t} \log \frac{a_\infty}{a_\infty - X}$$

where K is rate constant, t time in sec., a_∞ amount of nickel adsorbed at equilibrium time and X amount adsorbed at time t. The results for different concentrations of nickel chloride so obtained are recorded in Table I. The values of rate constants increased with increase in concentration of metal ion added, while the half life time decreased. This behaviour was characteristic of ion exchange process controlled by film and/or particle diffusion⁶.

An examination of data vide Fig. 2 revealed that pH influenced the adsorption of nickel by montmorillonites. The adsorption increased upto a pH value 6.0 and thereafter it declines. In the case of highest range of concentration of exchangeable cation added the adsorption was in the neighbourhood of CEC of the clay at pH value 5.5, adsorption beyond CEC appeared may be due to fixation and precipitation reactions as occurred with lapse of time.

An examination of the adsorption isotherms in dilute suspensions in the equilibrium concentration range 0 to 14 meq of nickel ions per litre at 30° and 60° indicated that the isotherms were similar to class L as defined by Giles *et al*⁸. There are also some inflexions followed by a linear portion. The initial convex curvature in the isotherms indicate that nickel met no strong competition for adsorption sites from water. The change of slope in all the isotherms are indicative of the saturation of adsorptive sites in the substrate. The linear rise thereafter indicates slow penetration of solute molecules into

the micropores till they are filled up. With rise in temperature from 30° to 60° adsorption decreases, i.e. there is a weakening of the attractive forces between the nickel and montmorillonites, which is indicative of exothermic types of interaction. A greater amount of nickel is adsorbed by base saturated montmorillonites than the acid saturated montmorillonites. Adsorption followed the order Na- mont. > H- mont. > Ca- mont.

The desorption results (Table 2) indicate that upto 90% of nickel adsorbed on the acid and base saturated montmorillonites can be desorbed by NaCl, KCl or BaCl₂. Such a behaviour is indicative of a physical type of adsorption.

TABLE 2—DESORPTION OF NICKEL BY DIFFERENT ELECTROLYTES FROM THE SODIUM-, CALCIUM- AND HYDROGEN-ION SATURATED MONTMORILLONITE-NICKEL COMPLEXES

Form of montmorillonite	Nickel adsorbed (meq/100 g clay)	Nickel desorbed (meq/100 g clay) by		
		NaCl	KCl	BaCl ₂
Hydrogen	71.8	68.1	63.8	64.8
Sodium	75.0	66.9	66.9	67.3
Calcium	72.1	64.0	64.8	64.9

The values of ΔE for adsorption of nickel on Na- and Ca-montmorillonites as determined by rate constants at 30° and 60° was found 10.2 to 10.6 k cal/mole respectively.

The relatively fast rate of adsorption, low values of activation energy and heat of activation (9.4 k

cal) and desorption studies suggest that the adsorption of nickel on montmorillonites is of physical type¹¹, involving vander Waals forces and hydrophobic bonding between the nickel and clay surface in an aqueous system.

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